

A Sentiment Analysis Case Study: Socializing about Social Distancing

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Abstract

Sentiment analysis is a process that uses natural language processing and machine learning to extract and identify the emotion associated with a text or an image. In the literature, we find different approaches to sentiment analysis that predominantly fall into two categories: machine-learning-based and lexical-based. When using machine learning for sentiment analysis, usually a classifier is required. When applying lexical-based methods, a list of known words, with each word having an associated sentiment, is used. The aim of the paper is to analyze the opinion of Instagram users towards the lockdown and social distancing caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, which spread rapidly worldwide at the beginning of 2020, with the use of various sentiment analysis tools. All the data collected for this study is public data gathered with the help of a tool called Phantombuster and is composed of over 15,000 posts. The posts were selected using several relevant hashtags and for the actual sentiment analysis process, Google Cloud was used. The collection and interpretation of the data are described in depth in this paper, providing suitable examples and possible explanations for the obtained result. The study might have importance for decision makers, but also for researchers, who have to choose or combine several sentiment analysis instruments in order to obtain meaningful results in their field of study.

Keywords: sentiment analysis tools; opinion about social distancing; opinions about COVID-10 pandemic; Instagram social network.

Introduction

Humans have always had the desire to express themselves, whether it is through their attires, their preferred activities, or their opinions regarding varying topics. With the rise of the Internet and different social media platforms, such as Instagram or Facebook, this desire became easier and easier to be fulfilled. Having this possibility of being heard is not only beneficial on an individual level but is also influential to the business landscape, especially but not exclusively when it comes to marketing. Companies are now able of gathering feedback in real-time from customers and can adapt their products to better fulfill their customers' needs and improve their strategy. Also, policy and decision makers can "hear" people voice before undertaking a certain action. This process of analyzing people opinions in online environments is called sentiment analysis and it is sustained by modern technologies, such as machine learning (ML) or natural language processing (NLP) tools. As it is said it generates a lot of economic value and improves our day-to-day lives, the current paper focuses on presenting a case study for sentiment analysis in the context of revealing various technologies, techniques, and tools for this. The case study is very actual, as we debate upon social distancing opinions in COVID-19 period on a well-

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known social network – Instagram. The case study underlines how a performant sentiment analysis can be done combining various tools in a newly developed web-application.

Supporting Technologies and Techniques for Sentiment Analysis

There are two main techniques for sentiment analysis: machine-learning-based and lexical-based [1]. When using machine learning for sentiment analysis, usually a classifier is required. Classifiers make use of data labels and generate tags, such as positive, negative, or neutral. However, as mentioned in [1], labeling could be time-consuming or not even allowed in some cases. The other approach is lexical-based, using a list of known words, with each word having an associated sentiment. Creating this dictionary is not easy nor complete as slang, for example, is rarely included [1].

There have been some comparative studies [1], [2], [3] between lexical-based and machine-learning-based sentiment analysis, each using different data sets and evaluation metrics. In [1] the authors compare eight sentiment analysis methods, which are considered among the most popular in scientific literature, and use two different datasets, a near-complete log of Twitter messages, collected throughout three and a half years and six sets of messages rated as positive and negative by humans. The methods compared are emoticons, Linguistic Inquiry, and Word Count (LIWC), SentiWordNet, SenticNet, SailAil Sentiment Analyzer (SASA), Happiness Index, and PANAS-t. All these methods were evaluated and compared in terms of coverage, degree of agreement, prediction performance, and polarity. The authors also implemented a web service based on a combined method that relies on the methods previously analyzed. They concluded that combining all the methods does not lead to the best performance but combining some of the methods, in terms of the data is the best approach.

Another comparison study is conducted in [2], where two machine-learning-based approaches, Naive Bayes (NB) and Support Vector Machine (SVM), and one lexical-based approach, SentiWordNet, are analyzed. The dataset used consisted of two online Indian news archives, from which the political news about two parties was extracted. Their focus was on the polarity and the implementation steps included tokenization, stop word removal, lemmatization, and pos tagging, performed using NLTK and Stanford POS tagger. Among the sentiment analysis methods, the best F-measure was SVM.

Furthermore, in [3] a supervised structured machine learning and a lexicon-based technique are compared. The lexicon-based sentiment classification was performed using Apache Hadoop and for the machine-learning method, Stanford Sentiment Treebank and Recursive Neural Tensor Network (RNTN) are introduced. The Treebank contains fully labeled parse trees constructed from movie reviews. The tests were based on a sample Zooniverse dataset and the experimental evaluation shows the RNTN method has a better performance score than the lexicon-based in terms of accuracy. However, the lexicon-based shows better performance on positive comments.

When it comes to lexical resources, a tool that is heavily mentioned in literature studies [1], [2], [4] is SentiWordNet. It is based on an English lexical dictionary called WordNet, which groups words into synonym sets, called synsets [4]. SentiWordNet assigns three different scores to a synset to indicate the sentiment of the text (positive, negative, and neutral); scores that have values of [0, 1] and add up to one [4]. In [1] the average score of a given text was determined by computing the synsets of all the words and comparing the positive and the negative scores. However, there are other approaches, such as [5], where an improved SentiWordNet, which modifies the objective words, is proposed. Given the advances made in machine learning and data mining, a considerable number of sentiment analysis research papers focus mostly on this approach. As previously mentioned, machine-learning tools use classifiers for determining the polarity of a word [6].

The approaches described so far focus only on textual sentiment analysis, however, some studies that explore sentiment analysis on visual content [7], [8], [9]. Some only propose solutions for visual sentiment analysis [7], while others try to combine textual and visual sentiment analysis methods [8], [9]. In [7], the authors used images from which they automatically extracted the so-called objective text description. They concluded that the objective text extracted from the pictures provides better results than the subjective text provided by the user and suggest that their methods could be used for other image-text association tasks. Compared to [7], the methods presented in [8] and [9] combine visual and textual sentiment analysis by using deep learning techniques. The authors of [8] propose a model in which visual and textual sentiment representations are obtained through multi-layer Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The visual sub-network consists of five convolutional layers and takes 244×244 pixels RGB images as input, while the textual sub-network uses pre-trained distributed representations of words. The two network representations are combined in a pooling layer. The method proposed was tested on two data sets the Visual Sentiment Ontology (VSO) dataset and the Multilingual Visual Sentiment Ontology (MVSO) dataset, and proved to be effective on VSO, having 1.3% accuracy gain [8]. Another approach to textual and visual integration for

sentiment analysis is explained in [9], where a bag of affective words (BoAW) that provides “visual cues” for sentiment analysis is introduced.

Sentiment Analysis Tools

Currently, there are several applications for sentiment analysis, each having features meant to address a specific purpose. Some are further described. MonkeyLearn [10] is a user-friendly machine learning platform for analyzing text. It uses a pre-trained sentiment analysis model and offers integrations with different applications, such as Excel or Google Sheets. Moreover, the platform allows the user to build a custom model for sentiment analysis; model that you can also test on the same platform. It has a free plan and multiple premium plans. Lexalytics [11] is another text-analysis tool, which focuses on the customer’s response to the business. It uses NLP to analyze the text and compiles the information in a visualization dashboard. The data is collected from social media platforms and has applicability in multiple domains, such as the airline industry. It does not have a free plan, as MonkeyLearn has. Brandwatch [12] is another platform that provides consumer insights. Compared with the previous two tools, Brandwatch also has an image insights tool that can identify images associated with a certain brand. This information extracted based on images includes metrics like mention volume, aggregate followers, and latest activity. Brandwatch is a tool for brand management that allows companies to monitor changes in sentiment, understand customer opinions, and track fluctuations in brand health. The platform is not free. Repustate [13] is another tool for assessing the sentiment behind a customer’s feedback. It has support for multiple languages, such as Chinese, French, and German, and can determine the sentiment behind slang, such as LOL, FYI and TBH, and also Emojis. Moreover, it allows the user to alternate meanings of words allowing full control over how the software analyzes customers’ feedback. It is not a free platform, too. Comprehend [14] is a service provided by Amazon that uses machine-learning algorithms to identify the sentiment of the customer. It has several features for discovering insights and relationships from data, such as identifying the language of the text or organizing a collection of text documents by topic. Unlike the other tools mentioned above, this tool does not offer a visual dashboard or platform, but rather a functional API, with a pay-per-use policy. Google Cloud [15] works similarly to Amazon, offering a large variety of services, among which a service for NLP, called Cloud Natural Language. The sentiment analysis tool identifies the author’s emotional opinion as positive, negative, or neutral. It supports a variety of languages, but unlike Amazon Comprehend one can, but is not required to specify the language of the text to be analyzed. If the language is not specified, it will be automatically determined when running the sentiment analysis method.

As it can be observed, each of the applications that are mentioned above has useful features, necessary to provide accurate sentiment analysis. Some of them are more versatile, letting business users customize their input more, while others are more restrictive in that sense. Furthermore, their price range varies a lot, with some being more affordable than others. A detailed analysis of these applications’ features is presented comparatively in the table below.

Table 1: Features Matrix for Sentiment Analysis Tools

	MonkeyLearn	Lexalytics	Brandwatch	Repustate	Amazon Comprehend	Google Cloud
Customizable sentiment models	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Visual Sentiment Analysis			✓			
Visual Dashboard		✓	✓			
Multiple Languages Support	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Free Option	✓				<i>Pay-per-use</i>	<i>Pay-per-use</i>
Categorize Data Based On Region			✓			
Slang Assessment				✓		
Emojis Assessment				✓		

A Case Study for Sentiment Analysis

As previously mentioned, sentiment analysis can be used to extract insights from public posts regarding different topics. In this paper, we have chosen to analyze the opinions of Instagram users towards the lockdown and social distancing from COVID-19 pandemic, which spread rapidly worldwide at the beginning of 2020. As tools, we used several ones, like Phantombuster, Google Cloud or Amazon Comprehend, but also created our own Node.js application, which calls other APIs.

Data collection

To automatically extract the data from Instagram, a specialized tool called Phantombuster [16] was used. Phantombuster has many automations (called “Phantoms”) that can extract data on behalf of a user from all major social networks and websites (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, Instagram or LinkedIn) and offers the possibility to create automations for custom websites as well. In this case, an Instagram predefined Phantom (Instagram Hashtag Collector) has been used to scrape public data, with the setup from Figure 1 - a. To scrape Instagram posts by hashtag, one must authenticate so the automation will act on his behalf, that is why a session cookie is provided for this setup. The number of posts it scrapes per hashtag is 5000 (Max Posts), keeping track of data and removing duplicates. The program runs every day and collects the data in CSV and JSON format. The targeted hashtags are specified in a public Google Spreadsheet, per row, in the first column: see Figure 1-b.

The figure shows the setup interface for the Instagram Hashtag Collector (a) and a Google Spreadsheet (b) used for specifying hashtags.

(a) Instagram Hashtag Collector Setup:

- Setup** (with **Edit** button)
- Session Cookie:** [Redacted]
- Spreadsheet Url:** <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets...>
- Extract Profile:** true
- Max Posts:** 5000
- Number Of Lines Per Launch:** 10
- Csv Name:** ig_hashtag_search
- Remove Duplicate:** true
- Launch:** Once per day

(b) Hashtags Spreadsheet:

	A	B
1	#stayhome	
2	#stayathome	
3	#stayhealthy	
4	#stayhomestaysafe	
5	#stayhomesavelives	
6	#coronavirus	
7	#corona	
8		
9		

Figure 1: (a) Instagram Hashtag Collector Setup. (b) Hashtags Spreadsheet for Sentiment Analysis

Analysis with Google Cloud

After gathering the data, it was analyzed with Google Cloud, since this tool is easy to integrate and work with. Initially, the data was organized as a JSON file, containing an array of over 25,000 posts. From this initial file, we extracted first the descriptions with more than three characters, obtaining an array with 24,940 posts. The sentiment detection API from Google needs the language of the input, and, for this, we used another API from Amazon Comprehend to detect the language of the posts. Since the file size was quite large, an asynchronous dominant language detection job for language detection was used. Amazon Comprehend examines the text to determine the dominant language, using identifiers from RFC 5646. The response contains a score that represents the confidence level that a particular language is a dominant language in the document. Using the language response, only posts having English as a dominant language were kept for further processing, the others being discarded. This is since all the posts that will be used for sentiment detection must have the same language. The remaining descriptions from the Instagram posts (over 15,000 posts) were written in a plain text file, line by line, and then analyzed with Google Cloud, like in Figure 2.

For the interpretation of the result, the maximum, the minimum, and the average of the scores and magnitudes were computed. The values of these computations are highlighted in Figure 5.

Scores			
(index)	max	min	avg
0	0.8999999761581421	-0.8999999761581421	0.22452158181807275

Magnitude			
(index)	max	min	avg
0	17.200000762939453	0	0.8117658727026378

Figure 5: Maximum, Minimum and Average of Scores and Magnitudes

Given these values, the posts with a score higher or equal than 0.2 are considered positive, the posts with a score between -0.2 and 0.2 are either mixed or neutral, and the posts with a score lower or equal than -0.2 are negative. The value of the magnitude is a key element for differentiating between mixed and neutral posts, a value higher or equal than 0.8 indicating a mixed emotion, while a value lower than 0.8 represents a neutral emotion. The threshold of 0.8 was chosen since it is close to the mean of magnitudes.

```
//interpretation
const positive = sentArray.filter((el) => el.score >= 0.2);
const negative = sentArray.filter((el) => el.score <= -0.2);
const neutral = sentArray.filter(
  (el) => el.score > -0.2 && el.score < 0.2 && el.magnitude < 0.8
);
const mixed = sentArray.filter(
  (el) => el.score > -0.2 && el.score < 0.2 && el.magnitude >= 0.8
);
```

Figure 6: Filtering of Sentiments

After categorizing the posts according to the sentiment that they possess, the result are presented in Figure 7.

```
{
  "positive":0.6128414939949848,
  "negative":0.048831991553385246,
  "neutral":0.2815758215652633,
  "mixed":0.05675069288636664
}
```

Figure 7: Sentiment Scores

The interpretation of the emotion extracted from the given text can be better visualized in the graph below, where the feeling expressed on Instagram during quarantine was mostly positive.

Figure 8: Pie Chart of Sentiment Scores

The fact that the sentiment score for the positive feeling was the highest could be regarded as unexpected, given that it was a difficult and stressful time for everyone. However, it is possible that due to the problems caused by the pandemic and the lockdown and also due to the abundance of worrying news that was broadcasted in a short period, people felt the need to share positive thoughts and be supportive and encouraging with each other.

Another important factor is the extra free time that a lot of people had while staying at home, which made some of them try new things or discover new passions like these individuals (sample from the collected data):

“5 Crazy Exercises using the socks 🧦 at Home 🏠 give it a try 🤸 #stayhome #fitterplanet #summervibes #fitnessvideo #armenia #yerevan #foryourpage #foryourlife #lesmills #onefamily”

“Quiche 🍷 What I love about this dish is that you can be so creative 😊 my version had spinach, mushrooms and feta cheese. By the way - it is spinach season right now 🥒 #quiche #stayhome #veggie #selfmade #baking #bakinglove #spinach #seasonalfood #seasonability #foodconcius”

Furthermore, a lot of businesses, such as gyms or restaurants, moved online during the lockdown and used platforms, such as Instagram to promote their services and attract customers. Online marketing has become quite essential for a lot of companies that managed to maintain a stable client base through the lockdown. Businesses who understood how to leverage this situation to their benefit continued to produce revenue or even had larger profits than before as people had more free time to invest in other activities, as previously mentioned.

*“Sunday's Online Classes 8:30 Am Deep stretch w/ Rasha Salhoub [...] **Payment methodsVia Bank transfer Or Vodafone cash: Or Payme store (will send you a link to pay via fawry) Please make sure to take a picture of your payment receipt and send it to us and will send you the link to the class. [...]”*

Additionally, there was a big movement for celebrating doctors and nurses who were on the frontline and who put a lot of effort to treat many incoming patients. Among the collected data several posts resembled this:

“Happy (Maryland) Health Care Heroes Day to all doctors, nurses EMTs, and first responders! 🚑🚒🚓👩🏻‍⚕️👨🏻‍⚕️👩🏻‍🔬👨🏻‍🔬👩🏻‍🏫👨🏻‍🏫👩🏻‍🎓👨🏻‍🎓👩🏻‍🎓👨🏻‍🎓👩🏻‍🎓👨🏻‍🎓 May 2nd, 2020: You are not just essential workers, you are front line heroes. The challenges you face on a daily basis, risking your own life and well-being of your families, is truly an inspiration. We thank you for all you have done and continue to do. ❤️❤️❤️❤️ [...]”

Finally, the second largest category of sentiments is represented by the neutral one and the reason for that is that not all Instagram users post images or videos with long descriptive captions, but rather, short, and concise ones.

Some users type descriptions formed by a couple of words or hashtags, while others add only emojis or choose solely to tag their friends in their photos. Examples of these types of descriptions can be observed below.

“#drawing #eyes #sketching #stayhome”

“👤👤👤 #selfportrait #stayhome”

“Veg pizza #stayhome #staysafe”

Moreover, a lot of users described their activities objectively, without any “emotion” that can be extracted from their input.

“Playing with my best dog park friend Uma (black dachshund) and new friend Chubby (pug mix)”

“This Corona virus has a very big ego, He will not come to your house unless you go out and invite him. Stay Home! #stayhome #staysafe #stayhealthy #keepsafedistance #stopspreadcovid #gitanjaliindia #teamgitanjali #love”

To sum up, based on this dataset, it can be concluded that people expressed mostly positive opinions during the lockdown from the beginning of 2020. While the individual intention of their posts is difficult to pinpoint, a hypothesis is that they wanted to find positive activities to focus on, as a distraction from the difficult reality of the time.

Conclusions

This paper presents a proof of concept for sentiment analysis used as a tool in determining the general feeling regarding a current problem. The data consists of over 15,000 public Instagram descriptions, written in English, and collected at the beginning of 2020. Amazon Comprehend was applied for the language selection, and Google Cloud for the sentiment analysis process. The score and magnitude of the posts were classified using the maximum, minimum, and average of these values. The overall feeling obtained based on the given assumptions was a positive one, which could be regarded as a peculiar result. There are some possible explanations for this result which were detailed before, such as discovering new passions or encouraging others in the pandemic context. While the individual intention of the posts is difficult to pinpoint, a hypothesis is that people wanted to find positive activities to focus on, as a distraction from the difficult reality of the time. We claim that the analysis can be useful for authorities to make decisions related to school starting or for business to make decisions related to their future expansion plans and the work is important for social network analysis research [17].

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